

Food and Agriculture
Organization of the
United Nations

The International Treaty
ON PLANT GENETIC RESOURCES
FOR FOOD AND AGRICULTURE

Vademecum for DOI Registrants

1 What is this document about?

The adoption of Digital Object Identifiers¹ (DOI) in the Global Information System² (GLIS) of the International Treaty offers a powerful tool for accurately and permanently identifying Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (PGRFA). However, the use of DOIs in this context is quite new and some practical information may be useful.

This document does not deal with how to register DOIs³, rather it focuses on what you can do with DOIs once they have been assigned to your collection, briefly describing how DOIs can be used in a variety of real-world cases.

To keep this document short and focused, inevitably, we had to simplify some concepts. If you are interested in more details, please refer to the GLIS page on the Treaty website at

<http://www.fao.org/plant-treaty/areas-of-work/global-information-system>

or send us an email at pgrfa-treaty@fao.org, we will be happy to provide all the clarifications you may need.

2 DOIs in SMTAs

The core purpose of the International Treaty is to facilitate access to PGRFA through the Standard Material Transfer Agreement⁴ (SMTA), a standard legal contract between Provider and Recipient that makes it very easy to obtain material under the Treaty's framework.

One of the stipulations of the SMTA is that the Provider, together with the material, must make available to the Recipient "All available passport data and, subject to applicable law, any other associated available non-confidential descriptive information".

A very simple and effective way to be in compliance with this requirement is just to indicate, in the Annex 1 to the SMTA, the DOIs of the PGRFA you are shipping! Why? Because the Recipient only needs to enter the DOIs in the GLIS home page⁵ to access the detail page on the DOI. This page contains:

¹ See <https://www.doi.org> for details

² See <http://www.fao.org/plant-treaty/areas-of-work/global-information-system>

³ For this, just send an email to pgrfa-treaty@fao.org and we will be happy to provide all the assistance you may require

⁴ See <http://www.fao.org/plant-treaty/areas-of-work/the-multilateral-system/overview>

⁵ <https://glis.fao.org/glis>. Please note that the DOI can be entered in any DOI resolution service (e.g. <https://www.doi.org>) to get to the detail page in GLIS

- all the passport information you have provided when you registered the PGRFA
- all links to external systems provided by you (or others, such as Genesys, WIEWS or EURISCO) where additional information on the PGRFA can be found
- links to publications and/or datasets related to the PGRFA (more on this below)

An example of a SMTA with DOIs in Annex 1 is shown in the following Figure 1. Note that, to make it very clear that the Sample ID is a DOI, the prefix "doi:" is used.

Figure 1: SMTA Annex 1 with DOIs listed as Sample ID

3 Citing DOIs in publications

One of the uses of PGRFA that the International Treaty most actively promotes is *scientific research*. Scientific research typically results in the dissemination of the findings through papers published in journals or books.

When a paper is published, it is good practice to provide an accurate and detailed list of the PGRFA that have been studied⁶ so that readers can search the Web for additional information. Now, from what we have said in chapter 2 above, what better than a DOI can provide super easy access to the information associated to a particular PGRFA?

This alone is a very good reason to list the DOIs of the PGRFA the paper refers to, but there is more.

As you probably know, most publications are assigned a DOI by their publishers. The DOI System now offers a service that records the *citations* of DOIs by other DOIs. In other words, there is a way for GLIS to automatically identify publications citing its own DOIs and list them at the bottom of the page as shown in Figure 2 below!

⁶ This is a particular instance of *data citation*, i.e. accurate, consistent and standardized referencing for datasets just as bibliographic citations are provided for other published sources like research articles

PGRFA doi:10.18730/9KYC

Citation: <https://doi.org/10.18730/9KYC>

Main descriptors | **Acquisition** | **DOI info**

Location	Centro Internacional de la Papa Av. La Molina N° 1895 - La Molina Lima Peru WIEWS code: PER001 [Details] Easy-SMTA PID: 00AD19	Biological status	Traditional cultivar/landrace
Local identifier	CIP 703314	Names	
Date	1976	Other identifiers	
Creation method	Acquisition	MLS status	Included
Taxon	Solanum stenotomum Juz. & Bukasov subsp. Stenotomum (Juz. & Bukasov) Hawkes	Historical	No
Common name	Potato		

Links to associated information (1-2 of 2)

Keywords	URL
Characterization, Passport data	http://genebank.cipotato.org/gringlobal/accesiondetail.aspx?id=21805
Passport data	https://www.genesys-pgr.org/10.18730/9KYC

Publications and datasets citing this PGRFA (1-1 of 1)

Type	Title	Published	Journal	Authors	Publisher
Paper	Genetic identity in genebanks: application of the SolCAP 12K SNP array in fingerprinting and diversity analysis in the global in trust potato collection	2018-05-24	Genome	D. Ellis, O. Chavez, J. Coombs, J. Soto, J. Coombs, R. Gomez, D. Douches, A. Panta, R. Silvestre, N.L. Anglin	NRC Research Press

Figure 2: Publications and datasets citing this PGRFA (bottom of the page)

The underlying technology⁷ is quite new and there are still a few glitches: for example, to make this work, it is currently necessary to list the GLIS DOIs in the publication *among other bibliographic references* as shown in Figure 3

IBPGR (1976) Report of IBPGR Working Group on Engineering, Design and Cost Aspects of Long-Term Seed Storage Facilities. Rome: International Board for Plant Genetic Resources. Google Scholar
IBPGR (1985) IBPGR Advisory Committee on Seed Storage: Report of the Third Meeting. Rome: International Board for Plant Genetic Resources. Google Scholar
IRGC 117265 https://doi.org/10.18730/1PG6J CrossRef Google Scholar
IRGC 117266 https://doi.org/10.18730/4WZGR CrossRef Google Scholar
IRGC 117267 https://doi.org/10.18730/4WZHS CrossRef Google Scholar
IRGC 117268 https://doi.org/10.18730/4WZJT CrossRef Google Scholar

Figure 3: GLIS DOIs among other bibliographic references

Sometimes, editors and publishers find this odd and might create difficulties, we are available to assist your authors in the discussion to get this through. In the meantime, we are actively working with the DOI System and publishers to identify alternative, more intuitive solutions to streamline this very useful service. We even offer the option of entering data into GLIS manually to streamline the process until it gets more widely spread. Just contact us at pgrfa-treay@fao.org!

⁷ A blog post by Crossref and DataCite addressed to publishers explains how cited DOI can be passed for this to work: <https://doi.org/10.5438/9456-sb49>

4 Citing DOIs in datasets

Scientific research often involves processing data organized in *datasets*. Datasets usually are the foundation of the research, but they can also be its output, or some of its outputs. For instance, a DNA sequence of particular PGRFA is a dataset that is studied, and the outcomes of this investigation are published. The dataset itself should be assigned a DOI to become a valuable piece of information that can be easily found and maybe reused in other experiments. Datasets are published by depositing them in repositories⁸ from which they can be accessed by interested users.

As for publications, the dataset's DOI can be related to the DOIs of the PGRFA whose information is organized in the dataset and this relationship can be identified by GLIS and made available to its users.

For this to happen, much like for publications, it is necessary that the GLIS DOIs of the PGRFA to which the dataset is related are provided when the DOI of the dataset is obtained. This is normally accomplished by filling in the repository's dataset deposit form that offers a suitable field in which the GLIS DOIs can be entered.

5 Receiving PGRFA that already has a DOI assigned

When you receive a PGRFA from another collection, maybe a DOI has been already assigned to it by the Provider. It is important to note that the DOI identifies the Provider's material and, among other information, reports the holder of the material (in this case, the Provider).

As PGRFA are living organisms, they can evolve and differentiate, especially when moved from one collection to another. Also, when a PGRFA is incorporated into a new collection, the Recipient becomes the holder of the received material. We recommend that a new DOI is assigned to the received material and such new DOI is related to the Provider's DOI, because:

- in many cases, genebank accessions are genetically heterogeneous. This means that, as you take some seeds from an accession bag to ship them to the Recipient, it is likely that the seeds in the shipment represent only a subset of the genetic identities present in the original seed bag. Assigning a new DOI to the material received is an effective way of keeping track of this.
- as said, the material may change over time and become progressively different from the original. Imagine a PGRFA that is transferred, say, 10 times from one Recipient to the next. It is not possible to guarantee that, after 20 years, the material at the end of the transfer chain is still precisely the same as the original. Therefore, to be able to properly identify the chain of transfers that led to the final material, it is necessary that a new DOI is assigned at each exchange and is related to its predecessor
- one of the mandatory descriptors associated to the DOI is the holder of the material. If a PGRFA is moved from collection A to collection B and from there to collection C, the only way in which we can know that C received the "version" of the PGRFA that was provided by B is to assign a new DOI at each step. Otherwise, it would appear that C received the material from A, i.e. the intermediary role of B would be completely obfuscated!
- if a Recipient publishes results on the material received, she should cite her own DOI, not the Provider's. Otherwise, it would appear that the study was carried out on the Provider's material that, as we have just seen, could be different from the original

Please note that Recipients are free not to register new DOIs for the material⁹ they receive (and therefore use the Provider's DOI) or register a new DOI without referencing the Provider's DOI as ancestor, but this would lead to the issues described above.

⁸ Example of public repositories are Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) or Figshare (<https://figshare.com>), but many institutions publish their datasets on their own websites

⁹ The booklet "Digital Object Identifiers for food crops" (<http://www.fao.org/3/I8840en/i8840en.pdf>) explicitly lists this option (not assigning a new DOI to the material but rather use the DOI registered by the Provider) as the "preferred default option for many general users" (see paragraph 10 Implementation for recipients of PGRFA, page 9). However, it also lists the issues that this choice would potentially imply.

Establishing the chain of relationships is also very useful for Providers as they will be able to see what is being done with their material, e.g. where it is transferred to and what publications and/or datasets are being produced studying it.

How can you reference the Provider's DOI when registering a new DOI for the material you just received? The answer is very simple, just indicate the Provider's DOI in descriptor R02: DOI(s) of progenitor(s) and specify Acquisition in descriptor M04: Method.

When proper relationships are established between a PGRFA DOI and the DOI(s) of its progenitor(s), GLIS is able to build a graph, such as the tiny example shown in Figure 4, that can be navigated to look for ancestors or descendant of the current PGRFA.

In the figure, we show two initial PGRFA (A and B, they are colored differently because we imagine them being conserved by different institutions). A and B are then transferred to other institutions (and new DOIs, C and D, are assigned and related to their predecessors A and B). C is further transferred to the final institution (green nodes) and is associated a new DOI, E. In the meantime, the same institution performs a selection on D obtaining a new PGRFA, identified by DOI F. Then E and F are crossed to create a new PGRFA that will be identified by DOI G. As you can see, how G was obtained is fully documented, something very valuable, especially for breeders and scientists.

Figure 4: PGRFA ancestry as DOI graph

6 Creating new PGRFA

Genebanks and breeders routinely process PGRFA in ways resulting in material that is genetically different from its predecessor(s) or that somehow needs to be discriminated from its ancestry. Assigning a new DOI to this material (and relating it to the predecessor(s)) is a very powerful yet convenient way of tackling these cases. The new DOI ensures that the new material is identified as different from the predecessor(s) yet it is related to it (or them) so that the ancestry of the material can be easily obtained.

The Guidelines¹⁰ and the Descriptors¹¹ documents describe in detail the real-world cases and the applications of each Method (descriptor M04). Depending on your specific case, when registering the DOI for the new material, indicate that Method in descriptor R04 and list the DOI(s) of progenitor(s) in descriptor R02 to correctly relate the new DOI to its ancestry.

Please refer to Figure 4 above for an illustration of this in relation to how F and G are obtained.

¹⁰ See <http://www.fao.org/plant-treaty/areas-of-work/global-information-system/guidelines>

¹¹ See <http://www.fao.org/plant-treaty/areas-of-work/global-information-system/descriptors>

7 Conclusion

The adoption of DOIs in GLIS has opened a whole lot of new possibilities, such as:

- improved data quality Documentation systems are being updated to accommodate the DOIs and new releases of popular Genebank Management Systems, such as GRIN-Global, now support DOI registration to GLIS. Also, information on PGRFA is being validated and amended as required in view of DOI registration
- facilitated system interconnection We now have a single and permanent identifier that can be reliably used across systems to point to the same material
- promoted accumulation of information Information scattered across different systems can now be reliably associated to the same material and becomes available to users
- increased visibility of your work GLIS promotes access to information *where it is created and maintained* through links to web sites, publication and datasets. This means more visibility for your collection, your website, and your scientific research